

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Computing Cell Type to Vasculature Distance Distributions

Quantitative analysis and visualization of cell proximity to vasculature in human tissue samples

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Introduction

This Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) outlines the methodology for computing the shortest distance from the centroid of various cell types (e.g., immune cells) to the nearest vasculature, commonly referred to as endothelial or blood vessel cells. This computation supports the creation of a VCCF (Vasculature Common Coordinate Framework) system. The SOP focuses primarily on the process to transform raw data into formats suitable for computation, running the VCCF code, and deploying resulting visualizations. To exemplify the process, the SOP uses skin Cell DIVE data from Ghose et al. 2023 but the process is organ and assay type agnostic.

The primary audience for this SOP includes research scientists, data analysts, and technicians involved in tissue imaging and analysis. Familiarity with Python programming and cell biology basics is assumed. The SOP does not cover advanced statistical analyses or organ-specific interpretations of the VCCF data and visualizations.

Roles and Responsibilities

Data Processor and Visualization Practitioner: Runs code to compute cell distances in relation to vasculature and visualizes resulting distance distributions.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Data Processor and Visualization Practitioner	Yingnan Ju Yashvardhan Jain	yiju@iu.edu yashjain@iu.edu

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Procedures

To accurately calculate the distances between various cell types and the nearest vascular structures, three process steps must be executed: Data preparation, distance computation, visualization deployment.

Data preparation [[Code Link](#) Line 96 - 224]

- Segmentation data verification
 - Review the 2D or 3D segmentation data. For the purpose of this SOP, data may come in two forms:
 - 2D Segmentation: Data are from thin (ca. 5-10 μm thick) slices of tissues.
 - 3D Segmentation: Data are from volumetric samples of tissues.
 - Verify the consistency of data. Inconsistencies can skew the computation results.
 - Ensure that all rows contain data in all essential columns, such as cell type, and coordinates on the x, y, and z axes.
 - Verify that the coordinates are within the desired numerical range, e.g., ensuring all coordinate values are greater than 0. Some datasets may include negative values. While negative values do not impact visualization spaces, if alignment with the raw image (which only has positive coordinate values) is necessary, the coordinates should be shifted to be positive values.
- Gather the raw data of cell positions.
 - Selection of relevant cells and markers.
 - Acquire data points for nuclei positions (`nuclei_x_list`, `nuclei_y_list`, `nuclei_z_list`), blood vessels (`vessel_x_list`, `vessel_y_list`, `vessel_z_list`).
- Set output paths.
 - Set root path (`output_root_path`).
 - Define output filenames for nuclei, blood vessel, and other (`nuclei_output_name`, `vessel_output_name`, `other_output_name`).

Distance computation [[Code Link](#) Line 226 - 317]

- Calculate blood vessel distance.
 - Iterate over each nucleus in the `nuclei_id_list`.
 - Initialize minimum distance to vessel.
 - If the nucleus type is in `cell_type_list` (e.g., immune cells), compute distance to nearest blood vessel.
 - Append computed distances to respective distance lists.

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- Update positions of the nearest vessel to their respective lists (nuclei_nearest_vessel_x_list, nuclei_nearest_vessel_y_list, etc.).
- Pseudo code:

```
function computeShortestDistances(data):
    if data is 2D:
        set z-dimensions = constant or unified value
    setupOutputPaths()
    defineCellTypes()
    if cell in CELL_TYPES:
        dest = BLOOD_VESSEL
    elif cell in DAMAGE_TYPES:
        dest = SKIN_SURFACE // This can be generalized to
        other types of distance-pair instead of skin-damage pair

    for each cell in data:
        if cell is in cell_type_list1:
            computeDistanceToNearestBloodVessel(cell)
        else:
            skip
    return computedDistances
```

- Optimize the calculation [[Code Link](#) Line 262 - 304]
 - The code uses an optimization technique for finding the nearest blood vessel to an immune cell in a 3D space, leveraging a threshold approach:
 - Setting a threshold:
Before starting the distance computations, an initial threshold distance (`_min_vessel_dist`) is set. This threshold represents the shortest known distance between the current immune cell and a blood vessel.
 - Preliminary Distance Check:
Before diving into an intensive distance calculation, the code first checks if the vessel is within the threshold on the x, y, and z axes. If the difference in coordinates on any axis exceeds the current threshold, there is no need to perform a more detailed distance computation as it is evident that this will not be the nearest vessel. This method reduces unnecessary computational cost, especially when dealing with many cells.
 - Detailed Distance Calculation:
Only if a vessel is within the threshold on all three axes does the code proceed to compute the Euclidean distance between the immune cell and the vessel using the formula:

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$$\begin{aligned} \text{distance} = \text{sqrt}((\text{cell's } x - \text{coord} - \text{vessel's } x - \text{coord})^2 \\ + (\text{cell's } y - \text{coord} - \text{vessel's } y - \text{coord})^2 \\ + (\text{cell's } z - \text{coord} - \text{vessel's } z - \text{coord})^2) \end{aligned}$$

■ Updating the Threshold:

If the computed distance is smaller than the current threshold, it indicates that a nearer blood vessel has been found. In this scenario, the threshold is updated with this newly found shorter distance. By using this threshold-based approach, the code efficiently narrows down the nearest blood vessel without having to compute the exact distance to every single vessel in the 3D space. This results in a significant speed-up, especially in datasets with large numbers of vessels and cells.

Results and visualization (optional) [[Code Link](#) Line 429 - 304]

- Use violin plots to visualize cell counts and distance.
 - Use plots, such as violin charts or histogram used in the [paper](#) and described in the [website](#), to showcase the distribution of cell distances.
- Implement interactive 3D visualizations of cell and biomarker distances. [[Result examples](#)]
 - Use Plotly 3D visualization package.
 - Visualize in two formats: 3D view of all cells and their shortest distances, and histograms showing distance distributions.
 - Optimize visualizations for online interactions.
- Visualization types for showing the vasculature distances:
 - Interactive 3D space visualization: Graphical representations that allow users to engage with and manipulate the displayed data in 3D space, typically in real-time.

Fig. 1. Interactive 3D space visualization example showing immune cells and distance to nearest endothelial cell

- Violin plots: Visual representations combining aspects of box plots and density plots to display data distributions.

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Fig 2. An example of violin plots showing distribution of distances of immune cells to the nearest endothelial cell and plotted by sun exposure and age

- Histogram: A graphical representation of the distribution of a dataset.

Fig 3. An example of a histogram showing immune cells and distance to nearest endothelial cell

References and Resources

The below references and resources were used in writing this Standard Operating Procedure.

Ghose, Soumya, Yingnan Ju, Elizabeth McDonough, Jonhan Ho, Arivarasan Karunamurthy, Chrystal Chadwick, Sanghee Cho, et al. 2023. “3D Reconstruction of Skin and Spatial Mapping of Immune Cell Density, Vascular Distance and Effects of Sun Exposure and Aging.” *Communications Biology* 6 (1): 718.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-023-04991-z>.

Code repository: <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/vccf-visualization-2022/tree/main>

Companion Website: <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/vccf-visualization-2022/>

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Glossary

Cell distance metrics: Measurement that represents the proximity between cell centroid and the outer boundary of vasculature cells.

Centroid: The geometric center of an object or shape, in this case, the geometric center of a cell nucleus.

Distance calculation: A mathematical computation to determine the shortest path between two given points. In 2D and in 3D space, we use the Pythagorean theorem; for 3D it is $(x_1-x_2)^2 + (y_1-y_2)^2 + (z_1-z_2)^2 = \text{distance}^2$, where x, y, and z are the coordinates of two cells.

Image segmentation: A process in digital image processing that divides an image into multiple segments or sets of pixels. Each segment corresponds to different parts or objects present in the image. In a medical context, it often refers to differentiating and labeling distinct structures or regions within a scan or microscopy image.

Nucleus: The cell nucleus (plural nuclei) is a membrane-bound organelle found in eukaryotic cells that contains most of the cell's genetic material.

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